

THE IMPACT OF THE ENGLISH BORROWINGS INTO UZBEK LANGUAGE AND CULTURE

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Abstract:

The article is devoted to the English borrowings into Uzbek language. In this article the synchronic aspects of the English borrowings are described to show present life time of Uzbek people their language and culture. The existing samples are analyzed as a language material.

Key words: borrowing, English equivalents, Uzbek culture, vocabulary enrichment, foreign words, tradition, impact, language.

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In the process of globalization, the interaction of different nations have a great impact on languages, cultures, and social life of people. As a result, by borrowing language units from one language into another there would be language changes, neologisms and archaic words appear, it is noticeable that everyday life of people start to change, their culture, tradition and behaviors vary as well.

In all languages borrowing is ordinary issue, borrowings are considered as the norm, just as they were used to broaden one's horizons and also because of the adoption of new words for an object or action. Therefore, Anglicism easily entered the language and became stronger in it. The study of borrowings is one of the most important problems in the range of linguistic research in conditions of intensive expansion of language contacts. No language can do without the natural and logical process of borrowing elements from other languages. Hence is the relevance of this study.

As it is mentioned above language is mirror which shows reality, a person's being in culture. According to J. Grimm, R. Raek, V. Humboldt, A. A. Potebnya interaction of language and culture is essential in linguistics.

In understanding of the issue with the relationship between language and culture, several approaches have been outlined. Under one of them, which is being developed by such philosophers as S.A. Atanovsky, G.A. Brutyan, E.S. Markarian, priority is given to the one-sided influence of culture on the language: with the change in reality, cultural and national stereotypes and the language itself change [Maslova, 1997, 34]. But by changing language units, there would be changes reality, culture and national stereotypes of people as well.

Famous linguist worked on this issue much and noted that language expresses specific features of the national mentality [Maslova, 1997, 35, 37]. At the same time, it is that "culture is included in the language, since it is all modeled in the text" [Maslova, 1997, 107].

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Agreeing with Maslova in our previous work it was introduced a new form in explanation lexical meaning of words, which is clearly delaminates between these two issues.

(Image 1)

Notions are our understanding concerning reality, but lexical meaning appears when we decide to convey certain notions and ideas through language units. [S.E. Shodiyev, 2014,65-72 p.] It is clear here that understanding of reality is in upper line which help us to realize that cultural issues are connected with human cognition. Second line is connected with language layer which is transport of reality.

Looking at this form visualize all the notes of linguists about language and culture. Language can be perceived as a component of culture or an instrument of culture [Tolstoy, 1991, 6]. Among the abundance of definitions of the concept of “culture” (according to some estimates, there are more than two hundred of them [Alefirenko, 1994, 31]), in our opinion, the most successful ones contain indirect or direct indications of the importance of language.

From above it is reasonable to say that language and culture cross in the same line as space and time. So, borrowed words from other languages convey and intesect in the same midpoint. And it should be mentioned that the speed of development of borrowed words also depends on the level of communication and the number of speakers. Every day at home and at work, a person uses foreign words in Uzbek and may not know that they belong to English language, since they are regularly and daily used when communicating at work, when buying things, while visiting sports institutions or a clinic.

At the present there are a lot of borrowed words that cannot be replaced. Uzbekistan has a wide range of contacts with the nations of the world. It is manifested in economic relations, culture, sport etc. Today, English words in Uzbek are actively used in our everyday life and they become integral, sometimes it is difficult to replace a concept spoken in English with one word in Uzbek. As a result, many English words are entering into Uzbek language. Some words connected with economy. For example, *cluster*, *paynet*, *plastic card*, and other borrowed words from English language seems to Uzbek people as they belong to their own language. At the same time, they can show that Uzbek people are using these entities in their everyday life.

The borrowed words as *hot dog*, *hamburger*, *sandwich* shows how the eating culture of Uzbek people dramatically changed. Because, it is not just food for eating, it is family traditions, going out all together in the evening and eating fast

food. Eating traditions moving to outdoors, it is not indoor tradition any more at least.

There are some sport games which are borrowed from English language as well. They are *football, basketball, tennis, hockey, table tennis* and others. All of them have already become a part of their lifestyle.

To conclude, language and culture walk along taking hand to hand. It can't exist one without the second. By integration of Uzbek people with English speaking countries, Uzbek language is enriching own vocabulary system through borrowing words from English language. At the same time, different cultures issues coming into the life of Uzbek people.

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